

A Review of e-Waste Management and Its Challenges in Kenya

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of this paper was to provide an overview of the current state of e-waste management in Kenya. The study constitutes literature reviews of electronic articles published since the year 2011, sourced from journals, media, and organizational websites. The review examined various aspects of e-waste management, such as product recovery, material recovery, energy recovery, and safe disposal practices. Besides highlighting the extent of waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE), the paper outlines the risks presented by unregulated and improper e-waste disposal and provides recommendations for improving e-waste management in Kenya. The recommendations from the study include the involvement of the informal sector and other stakeholders in raising awareness of the risks associated with rudimentary e-waste treatment, proposing policy adjustments that consider wide stakeholder participation, and introducing training programs in technical colleges and universities specifically addressing the issue of WEEE. It further proposes initiatives both at the national and county levels that would foster discussions and debates on the e-waste menace to minimize adverse effects on humans and the environment. This is expected to help Kenya in the advancement of several goals, including Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Vision 2030, and meet its constitutional obligations.

Keywords: e-Waste, Electronic Waste, WEEE, e-Waste Management, Kenya

1. INTRODUCTION

The safe disposal of electrical and electronic waste (e-waste) has been a challenge that predates the 1980s but has recently received increased attention globally, because of the exponential growth in the production and utilization of electrical and electronic products (EEPs) (Kimeli, 2014; Kumar & Holuszko, 2016). Locally, despite being a relatively recent addition to the category of serious hazardous waste, it has received significant research limelight because of the challenges it poses to human health and the environment if not properly managed (Songa & Lubanga, 2015; Kaloki, 2014; Tocho & Waema, 2013). The global technological revolution, consumerism behaviour exhibited by users of EEPs, improved disposable income, and the deteriorating quality and lifespan of imported EEPs are some of the factors that have collectively made WEEE the fastest-growing waste stream in the world (Lundgren, 2012; Ofuya & Mulinge, 2023; Kwame, 2021).

In Kenya, the problem has been exacerbated by the exponential growth in the application of mobile phones, the government's industrialization program, and the adoption of solar-powered equipment (Odenyo, 2022). The COVID-19 pandemic caused a further spike in the utilization of information communication technology (ICT) and the associated electronic devices because many businesses went online (Ngila, 2020; Adejumo & Oluduro, 2021). More recently, Kenya transferred several government services onto e-platform in its digitization process requiring its citizenry to obtain and pay for the services electronically in what may further increase e-waste volumes in the near future. Due to the anticipated increase of e-waste, there is a lot of pressure on underdeveloped countries to come up with environmentally robust e-waste management systems and sound policy initiatives to forestall the imminent e-waste disposal crisis occasioned by the increased uptake and imports of electrical and electronic equipment (EEE) (Asante et al., 2019). As of the year 2012, up to 80% of e-waste generated in developed countries ended up in developing countries for disposal, often disguised as donations by foreign organizations (Lundgren, 2012; Balasubramanian et al., 2019).

The UN adopted sustainable development goals (SDGs) and aspires to protect the environment and ensure the good health and well-being of humanity. This underscores and prioritizes the need for management of WEEE, which is a cross-cutting issue in the SDGs (Forti et al., 2020). To realize the globally acclaimed circular-economy model, e-waste must receive considerable attention (Mbuthia, 2023). Developed countries have successfully demonstrated that sustainable and sound e-waste management is feasible. This is evident in countries like Japan, Switzerland, and Canada, where management models such as 'take-back systems' are fully established and functional (Africa Clean Energy-Technical Assistance Facility (ACE-TAF), 2019; Kumar & Holuszko, 2016). In Canada, the Canadian government regularly conducts audits and issues licenses to recycling and refurbishing firms to operate within a government-regulated framework (Kumar & Holuszko, 2016). Ghana, as a case of a developing nation, has implemented a comparatively functional take-back and recycling system ACE-TAF, 2019). However, for most developing countries, there is generally a lackluster approach in dealing with the mounting e-waste problem, which is of great concern and is a setback in the overall

global effort of managing the increasing volumes of e-waste. A report highlighting the scenario in Asia singles out legislation and enforcement of specific laws addressing e-waste management as being a major overarching challenge (Honda et al., 2016; Borthakur & Sinha, 2013). The developing countries are beginning to establish e-waste management practices and regulatory frameworks, but most are at their elementary stage and often are substantially inadequate in effectively tackling the e-waste menace (Borthakur & Sinha, 2013; Muhani, 2012; Mmereki et al., 2015).

Kenya lags in several aspects of e-waste management. For example, a paltry 10% of e-waste generated in the country is managed properly, yet Vision 2030 aspires to have high economic and social development while prioritizing a sustainable environment (NEMA, 2011). Despite having achieved certain legislative milestones, Kenya is yet to fully implement and enforce e-waste-specific policies and legislation that effectively facilitate sustainable e-waste management (ACE-TAF, 2019; Anyango & Munyugi, 2018; Muniafu & Miya, 2016; Chege, 2021; NEMA, 2011). WEEE is a cross-cutting issue that touches on several ministries, departments, and government agencies (MDAs), and its management is done through various guidelines, standards, and regulations from the MDAs. Currently, e-waste management in Kenya is governed by several acts, including the Environmental Management and Coordination (Amendment) Act, 2015, and the Sustainable Waste Management Act (2022). These acts, among other provisions, establish the legal framework for the management and conservation of the environment as well as the handling of hazardous waste and pollutants both at the national and county levels (NEMA, 2011). Further, the National ICT policy developed by the Ministry of Information, Communication, and Digital Economy (MoICDE) and published in the year 2019 underscores the government's commitment to formulate policies and regulations for sustainable electronic waste management (Wambui, 2021).

A more recent endeavour undertaken by the Kenya government in the implementation of specific e-waste regulation is the development of the 'National E-Waste Management Strategy' which is a five-year blueprint that among other aspirations, is aimed at enhancing regulatory framework to facilitate effective and sustainable management of e-waste at the county and the national levels (Khaduli, 2022). Despite these efforts, Kenya's response to the global issue of e-waste has been slow. Apart from deficiencies in the legal and policy framework, management of e-waste in Kenya grapples with multiple challenges, ranging from the illegal influx of e-waste to a lack of adequate awareness among key stakeholders (Otieno & Omwenga, 2015). There is also a lack of appropriate infrastructure and technology to support the collection, transportation, and recycling of e-waste (Omari, 2018). These shortcomings and deficiencies have given rise to increased risks to the environment and human health as a result of improper handling of e-waste.

In a country where a robust and sustainable e-waste management system is lacking, important parameters such as e-waste volumes and sources cannot be established, and consequently, the extent of the e-waste situation cannot be accurately determined (MoEF, 2019). This exposes

Kenya to vulnerabilities such as being a dumping site for e-waste by other countries. Effective e-waste management depends on implementing strategies that involve close collaboration with key stakeholders in the industry.

1.1 Research Objective

The landscape of e-waste management in Kenya has experienced notable shifts over the years, particularly in how e-waste is managed from the consumer end to disposal. The main objective of the study is to gain an understanding of the current state of e-waste management aspects and identify inherent challenges and gaps to propose recommendations based on global good practices, outlining the steps that the Kenyan government can adopt to ensure sustainable and safe handling of e-waste.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 What is e-waste, and why is it an Issue

E-waste is a broad term that encompasses a variety of electrical and electronic gadgets and their parts that are of no use for future reuse or value to the first or original owner (Ofuya & Mulinge, 2023). It includes household electronic and electrical appliances, medical equipment, toys with electrical and electronic parts, and their casings (Srivastav et al., 2023). Various definitions for WEEE exist, and currently, there is no universally accepted standard definition (Mmereki et al., 2015). The lack of an internationally agreed standard definition can be a source of great disparities in the quantification of e-waste globally and has even raised controversies in the application of the Basel Convention for the control of transboundary e-waste movement (Wang & Liu, 2020; Lundgren, 2012; Franz & Silva; 2021). Some definitions are more general, while some are country-specific and may depend on associated legal obligations (Honda et al., 2016).

For instance, one definition terms e-waste as ‘electrical and electronic equipment and its parts that have been discarded by its owner as waste without the intention of reusing’ (ITU (Information Telecommunication Union), 2021). The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) defines e-waste as ‘Any appliance using an electric power supply that has reached its end-of-life’ (Balasubramanian & Karthik, 2016). E-waste can also be defined based on its performance. In Kenya, e-waste includes used electronic equipment with hazardous substances that are meant for further reuse, resale, repair, recycling, or disposal, and whose functional state does not serve any good purpose to the current owner (Amolo, 2017). This means that an electronic device could still be functioning and has not reached the end of life (EoL), but still be categorized as e-waste from the perspective of the first user. The life cycle of EEP begins with the extraction of virgin materials, which are used in the factories to manufacture the product. Then it enters the consumer use phase before the waste management phase, then lastly, the disposal of the EoL phase (Massa & Archodoulaki, 2023).

Reports indicate that the global e-waste generation exceeded 50 million tonnes in 2019, which is about 21 times the figures recorded 5 years earlier (Srivastav et al, 2023; Ofuya & Mulinge,

2023; Forti et al., 2020). This exponential growth is estimated to continue at the rate of 3-5% yearly, which is about 3 times the growth rate of other solid wastes combined (Ambetsa, 2021; Kumar et al., 2021). At this rate, improperly handled e-waste poses considerable risks to the environment, further exacerbating the negative impacts caused by other factors such as climate change and loss of biodiversity (Mbuthia, 2023; Kwame, 2021; Mosonik, 2020). To illustrate this, while global e-waste was only 2% of all the solid waste in landfills in the year 2019, it contributed to about two-thirds of heavy metal toxins (Ngila, 2020). This disproportionate impact can be largely attributed to the presence of heavy metals, including mercury, lead, chromium, and nickel, which persist in the environment due to their non-biodegradable nature (Gangwar et al., 2017). These and other hazardous substances infiltrate into water bodies, accumulate in soils, or escape to the atmosphere as fumes or dust, contaminating and polluting the environment (Srivastav et al., 2023). The pollutants can then be ingested, inhaled, or absorbed through the skin at levels detrimental to human health, either directly or through sources such as edible plants, animals, or air (Asiimwe & Ake, 2012; Srivastav et al., 2023). Health-related issues will also arise that are associated with climate change, mainly brought about by the pollutants in the atmosphere. (Bhutta., 2011; Mosonik, 2020). Research also shows that there is a strong correlation between informal treatment of e-waste and environmental and health problems, especially in children (Ankit et al., 2021). The extent to which a person's health is affected is directly linked to the extent of exposure and the type of hazardous compounds (Nti et al., 2021).

The composition of WEEE is complex, and effective treatment is also an equally complex and expensive process requiring special skills and resources (Srivastav et al., 2023; Lundgren, 2012). E-waste is heterogeneous, comprising a complex mixture of plastics, glass, rubber, ceramics, metals, and other toxic and non-toxic materials assembled or put together in a non-standard way during the manufacture of EEPs (Lundgren, 2012; Srivastav et al., 2023). The Plastics used are proving to be the largest growing contaminants among the constituents of e-waste (Ghimire & Ariya, 2020). There are other forms of contaminants present in e-waste, some of which are persistent and could be dispersed through modes such as air, soil, water, or direct contact. In significant amounts, the substances can have severe environmental and health effects (Cayumil et al., 2016). The rapid technological changes further influence the composition and features of EEPs, complicating the automation of the treatment process of e-waste (Srivastav et al., 2023). The low concentration levels of certain reusable substances are yet another setback in attracting investors into the formal recycling process.

Managing the large number of stakeholders with varying interests demands a multi-disciplinary approach to the global WEEE problem, which is often a challenge. The key stakeholders in this industry include the government, which includes policymakers, the private sector, which includes manufacturers, distributors, retailers, and importers of EEPs, the civil society, regulatory agencies, inter-governmental organizations, and the informal sector (Ambetsa, 2021). Waste is also a cross-cutting issue touching on the economy, technology, energy, waste management, human health, international affairs, social concerns, and even climate change.

(Ghimire & Ariya, 2020) Policymakers find it a challenge to formulate policies that effectively address the diverse interests of the various groups. Developing nations are home to large numbers of poor people, and this is where the impacts of WEEE will be felt the most. Up to 80% of e-waste destined for recycling ends up in developing countries like Ghana, Nigeria, and India because of cheap labor and weak legislation (Lundgren, 2012). Other consignments are shipped to the developing nations through illegal e-waste trading often disguised as second-hand goods for donation (Wang et al., 2020; Lundgren, 2012) further complicating efforts to get accurate figures of e-waste in these regions (MoEF, 2019).

Certain substances present in e-waste contribute to global warming when released into the environment, particularly during the treatment process. Examples of such substances include chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs) and Hydrofluorocarbons (HFCs), usually found in some refrigerating and air conditioning equipment (Cayumil et al., 2016). Forte (2019) observed that up to 98 million metric tonnes of carbon dioxide (CO₂) equivalents were emitted into the atmosphere by e-waste from fridges and air-conditioning systems that were improperly managed in the year 2019. In light of these concerns, there has been increased research and innovation to substitute chlorine-based refrigerants in refrigeration systems with alternative refrigerants that have lower global warming potentials (Benhadid-Dib & Benzaoui, 2012).

As a nation develops economically, there is typically a corresponding improvement and expansion of telecommunication infrastructure, which in turn increases the utilization of modern electronic communication equipment for various purposes such as entertainment, commerce, health, and socializing. Similarly, when the gross domestic product (GDP) of a country improves, consumption of EEE increases (Forti et al, 2020). When people have enough disposable income, they can afford a variety of EEPs, including refrigerators, microwaves, dishwashers, dry-cleaning machines, etc. This will in turn increase the rate of e-waste generation (Baldé et al, 2017). Collectively, these factors compound the complexity of sustainable e-waste management. The multiple threats posed by e-waste to humans and the environment, however, serve as the force behind increasing concern and the search for solutions.

2.2 E-waste Management Options

One important step towards reducing the volumes and the negative impacts of WEEE on the environment is the implementation of proper management practices (Borthakur & Sinha, 2013). The key elements necessary for the efficient management of e-waste include cost-effective collection infrastructure, a functional recycling industry, and supportive functions such as awareness creation, adequate funding, good policy and legal framework, and proper monitoring and reporting systems (Ternald, 2019). The government of Rwanda has earned recognition for notable achievements in e-waste management. The success has been achieved through establishing strategic partnerships with private organizations and various stakeholders in the development and implementation of a comprehensive collection system, an advanced

legal and regulatory framework, and building a recycling plant (Tetra Tech International Development, 2021).

Good management strategies for e-waste should be prioritized to check the high rate of generation and to safeguard the environment against contamination (Srivastav et al., 2023). Researchers have proposed various strategies that generally include the following aspects. To begin with, they advocate for a reduction in the use of hazardous substances during the design and manufacturing stage using substitution with less hazardous, biodegradable, or renewable substances and/or components that are easily recyclable or reusable components or create durable products (Bridgens et al., 2017). Secondly, the re-use of EEE through repair, repurposing, refurbishing, and/or re-manufacturing to extend the useful lifespan of an EEE before recycling. Re-manufacturing in this context involves reconditioning a production process to make more or less a new product. Repair is the last phase before an EEE is recycled. It entails the fixing of a faulty product to enable reuse by the owner or resale to another party. Refurbishing has an aspect of some repair to make an old product look new (Massa & Archodoulaki, 2023). These processes constitute what is known as product recovery.

The next strategy focuses on the recovery of value from WEEE. This is done through component or material recovery, which constitutes what is commonly known as recycling. Recycling is a mechanical and/or chemical process for recovering components or materials and/or energy from WEEE. The materials recovered are used for either the original purpose or other purposes (Bridgens et al., 2017; Srivastav et al., 2023). Recovery of the materials for re-use can save the resources that are scarce or rare (Srivastav et al., 2023). Recycling also minimizes air and water pollution that would have been occasioned by virgin mining of rare minerals, thereby mitigating climate change effects (Ankit et al., 2021). Energy recovery is where energy is conserved by using recycled materials as opposed to using primary or virgin materials (Yken et al., 2021). The recovered materials can also be used as catalytic elements in energy conversion processes (Seif et al., 2023). Lastly, disposal must be done in an environmentally responsible and sound manner by incineration or landfilling. The previous processes of reducing, reusing, and recycling should ensure that the quantities or residues of hazardous substances in WEEE remaining for disposal in the last process are minimal. Wambui (2021) summarizes the activities from the most preferred strategy to the least preferred as prevention, minimization, reuse, recycling, energy recovery, and disposal.

To ensure effective e-waste management, there must be a supportive and operational policy and legal framework to standardize and enforce implementation, as well as good training and sensitization programs (Wibowo et al., 2021). The European Union has the highest recycling rates of e-waste in the world, which is attributed to very strong directives and standards (Yken et al., 2023). Their policy and legislative framework have been instrumental in the transition towards a circular model economy, an approach that is very effective in managing e-waste through implementing sustainable production and consumption of materials in a closed-loop system (Shevchenko et al., 2019; Srivastav et al., 2023). In this system, materials and products

are kept in use for longer periods, extending their lifespan through reuse processes. It is possible to do proper handling of e-waste based on voluntary initiatives of industry players, which necessitates a behavioural change from all stakeholders who recognize the importance of taking responsibility for their respective roles (Srivastav et al., 2023). However, success has been largely realized where there is some form of incentive to improve collection and disposal systems. Some are monetary, with some being economic incentives (Shevchenko et al., 2019).

Funding is a critical component of the sustainable e-waste management system. This is because the expenses associated with formal recycling activities of e-waste would often exceed the revenues accruing from the sale of materials or products recovered from the waste (Cycle Consulting, 2015). Therefore, a sound financing scheme that addresses the issue of sustainability of operations in the e-waste value chain must be in place (Baldé et al., 2017). Several financing models may be considered. One example is the Advanced Recycling Fee (ARF), which has the fundamental working concept of Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR). The approach has been lauded as a good and manageable form from the point of view of social welfare and manufacturers (Shan et al., 2021). The government fully manages the administrative aspects of the system by determining and imposing a fee for every new or refurbished EEP (Shan, 2021). The fee is imposed upfront to cater for the costs associated with the collection, sorting, transportation, treatment, and environmentally sound disposal of e-waste. Consumers are not charged any fee for bringing e-waste to the official collection centers (Mohana et al., 2020). This method has worked successfully in Switzerland and California (Muniafu & Miya, 2016; Shan et al., 2021).

In the EPR system, mainly used by European countries, the producer is responsible for take-back logistics (collection and transportation), treatment, and disposal of e-waste (Yunita et al., 2019). The system has been recommended as a viable option for adoption in the Kenyan system of e-waste management (Anyango & Mjuyungi, 2018). However, one drawback of the system is that it may not give adequate consideration for re-use and re-furbishing to extend the lifespan of e-waste which could be more suitable for developing countries like Kenya. Under the system, the consumer is only required to return the malfunctioning and disused EEP to the official collection centre (Shan et al., 2021). A modified EPR approach is employed in Japan, where the consumer shares responsibility with producers by paying a pre-disposal fee (PDF) while returning the e-waste to collection centres. The disadvantage of this system is that consumers may choose to dispose of e-waste irresponsibly or illegally, circumventing the intended responsible disposal process (Shan et al., 2021). Several other modified forms of EPR allocate various responsibilities across the e-waste value chain (Cycle Consulting, 2015).

Establishing a formal e-waste management system is very expensive initially, requiring extensive capital input and technical expertise to develop the necessary infrastructure (Lundgren, 2012). Setting up such a system in every country is not even feasible due to the requirements. The initial stages of a formal recycling process involve the decontamination of WEEE, which is the. Removal of liquids and other gases, followed by dismantling, which is

the mechanical separation and segregation of various components. The valuable, hazardous, and non-hazardous materials are separated and handled differently. The resulting residues are shredded to reduce the size, after which special treatment is applied. The final stages include recycling and incineration for energy recovery (Omondi et al., 2022). The mixed formal and informal system has huge opportunities for the urban poor individuals and small companies involved in the harvesting and sale of valuable materials (Shevchenko et al., 2019). This can be a profitable economic activity if harnessed well and adequate sensitization is carried out (Gollakota et al., 2020). The value of WEEE in terms of reusable raw materials was estimated at 57 billion dollars, which is a good opportunity to make wealth if properly managed (Ghimire & Ariya, 2020). The creation of green jobs and the subsequent development of a green economy will aid in the poverty eradication process (Baldé et al., 2015).

3. METHODOLOGY

There is a dearth of published information concerning e-waste management in Kenya. This notwithstanding, we endeavoured in this study to use the available data from multiple secondary sources. Given that the primary intention of the research is to provide insight based on a broad understanding of the subject matter, we begin by looking at selected aspects of e-waste management from a global perspective. We reviewed relevant literature in academic materials, scientific research reports, technical manuals, government reports, and reports by developmental agencies. Regarding the Kenyan perspective, we relied mainly on articles and reports from the Kenyan government, international organizations and agencies, newspaper publications, personal sources, as well as academic literature. When selecting the sources, we considered the reputation of journals and publishers, and the dates of publication. The set criteria excluded articles lacking publication dates, those with unclear authorship, and publications released before the year 2011. Our rationale for using the year 2011 as the cut-off date for source inclusion is informed by study findings indicating a surge in mobile subscriptions in Kenya from 114,000 in the year 2000 to 24.9 million in the year 2010 and 28 million in 2011, foreshadowing a subsequent increase in the utilization of electronic devices (Cherutich, 2013). Given that mobile phones constitute a major source of e-waste, it is reasonable to conclude that the e-waste issue became prominent in Kenya around the year 2011 up to the present day (Omari, 2018). Using search keywords (individually or in various combinations) such as e-waste, Electronic Waste, WEEE, Management, Developing Countries, and Kenya, we selected relevant literature mainly from online journals, archival databases, and websites.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 E-Waste Management, Kenya Scenario

The world's most pressing environmental concern is centered around developing countries because of their vulnerability and the level of preparedness to address environmental issues. These issues include climate change and environmental pollution arising from sources such as WEEE, plastic waste, and toxic effluents (Mosonik, 2022; Ofuya & Mulinge, 2023). The negative effects of these developments on the environment are enormous and some are irreversible. Kenya, in its Vision 2030 blueprint, envisioned a country with an efficient and

sustainable waste management system through strategies that involve proper handling and recycling of waste (NEMA, 2015). While there has been some steady progress toward the achievement of the objective, significant tangible results have not been realized so far (Ofuya & Mulinge, 2023). The country continues to grapple with serious ecological and environmental crises, ranging from high levels of pollution of water bodies by toxic effluents to an increasing influx of WEEE from other countries (Wangari, 2023; Anyango & Munyungi, 2018).

Each year, Kenya currently generates an estimated 17,000 to 51,3000 metric tonnes of e-waste, and there is potential for these figures to rise to unsustainable levels if adequate management strategies are not implemented (Shevchenko et al., 2019; Ofuya & Mulinge, 2023; Waema & Mureithi, 2008; Kwame, 2021). Kenya has shown some level of goodwill by developing and implementing several strategies at the national level that include appropriate legislation, relevant policies, standards, and regulations that guide the sustainable management of e-waste. Private actors and non-governmental organizations have also come on board to assist the government in the environmental conservation and protection initiative. For example, the Electronic Waste Initiative (EWIK) has been instrumental in raising awareness among the youth on the proper recycling of e-waste through repairing faulty laptops. WEEE Centre, a company located in Nairobi, engages in recycling and proper disposal of e-waste (Africanews, 2023).

Despite all these efforts, the challenges seem persistent and have become increasingly pronounced at the county level. Where similar initiatives are beginning to take shape. Several Counties, including Bungoma, Nakuru, and Machakos Counties, have taken the lead in addressing these challenges. Working in collaboration with NEMA, the Nakuru County administration has devised plans for establishing official collection centres for e-waste, while Machakos County has already developed an act that specifically addresses the issue of e-waste (Khaduli, 2023; Kenya Law, 2016). WEEE enters Kenya illegally through porous borders and is also generated locally through imports of EEE. Mainly from China (Muniafu & Miya, 2023). Several government initiatives and programs have largely and indirectly contributed to the sudden increase in volumes of e-waste in Kenya. For instance, the Digital Literacy Programme (DLP) for public primary schools introduced millions of electronic devices in the country in 2017 and subsequent years. (Ministry of Information, Communication and Digital Economy (MoIDE), 2023). Soon, other government programs like the Constituency Innovation Hubs (CIH), Jitume, Ajira Digital, and Made-in-Kenya Smartphone will lead to the importation and assembly of more electronic devices to be used for accessing online content and government e-services (MoIDE, 2020).

A baseline survey conducted to establish the status of e-waste in Nairobi highlighted the level of uncontrolled disposal of e-waste. It revealed that up to 50% of e-waste from refurbishes is sold to the informal market for recycling, where it is often treated in a rudimentary manner (Muniafu & Miya, 2016). The unregulated private sector also participates in the recycling process. But often lack the requisite infrastructure and skills for proper and safe treatment of

e-waste (Omari, 2018). A similar study showed that 40% of e-waste in Nairobi is disposed of alongside other solid waste without separation (Kaloki, 2014). The management of e-waste is mainly done by the informal Jua Kali sector, which engages in economic activity to meet and sustain their subsistence requirements. This sector consists mainly of metal scrap dealers and component scavengers who look for valuable materials for repairing other faulty EEE or resale in the second-hand market. Metal scrap dealers usually cherry-pick metals such as aluminum, steel, copper, and iron for export. According to one study, scrap dealers handle about 18% of e-waste in Kenya (Kaloki, 2014).

The Jua Kali artisans also engage in the pre-treatment process of e-waste, where they remove easily detachable and reusable parts (Ofuya & Mulinge). The dismantling and segregation are done manually and in an unregulated environment, and without proper protection for the workers (Muniafu & Miya, 2016). In a study carried out in Nairobi, only 3% of informal workers were reported to be wearing safety gear while working, and most of the workers were unaware of the health risks posed by e-waste. This lack of awareness is also observed among consumers who are unaware of the health and environmental effects of e-waste (Kaloki, 2014). Besides the lack of awareness, several studies have identified a lack of or weak policy and legal framework, limited technical know-how, insufficient infrastructure, improper collection system, and poor disposal methods as the main setbacks in the proper management of e-waste in Kenya (Ofuya & Mulinge, 2023; Kwame, 2021). NEMA, the lead agency in Kenya responsible for environmental conservation, has been criticized for its inability to effectively address the pollution in the country. NEMA was established by the EMCA Act, 1999 with the legal mandate of implementing government policies on the environment, yet its impact has not been felt and has been termed as 'toothless' in terms of conservation efforts with the main challenges being inadequate financing, under-staffing, competition with other government agencies and, issues related to corruption. (Wangari, 2023).

4.2 E-waste Generation

Accurate data on the volumes of e-waste generated globally every year is not easy to obtain, partly due non-standardized manner of defining what constitutes e-waste (Mmereki, 2015). The global figures were approximated to be around 53.6 million metric tonnes in 2019, with a projected increase to about 74 million metric tonnes in the year 2030. Unfortunately, only 17.4% of this is properly managed, which underscores the sorry state of affairs (Forti et al, 2020). The numbers vary between countries depending on factors such as the economy of the country and population growth (Forti et al., 2020). In Kenya, the available data shows that about 17,000 to 51,300 metric tonnes of e-waste is generated annually, and just between 1% to 17% is recycled or managed properly (UNEP, 2014; Amadala, 2019). In the year 2012, e-waste in Kenya was estimated to be about 3000 metric tonnes and had grown 17 times more by the year 2021 (Africanews, 2023). Due to a large portion of e-waste being handled sub-optimally alongside other municipal waste, most of it ends up in places like Dandora dumpsite and Nairobi River. Scavengers recover whatever is valuable for reuse. They may also resell these

salvaged items or components to middlemen with knowledge of the market for the recovered e-waste materials (Omari, 2018).

Several recent activities and events have led to an increased generation of internally or domestically generated e-waste in Kenya. With the advent of the COVID-19 pandemic. Most businesses were compelled to adopt the use of digital devices, and in Kenya, businesses are known to contribute a substantial amount of e-waste (Adejumo, 2021). The government has also intensified the use of digital platforms for delivering services and promoting green energy, all of which will collectively lead to increased use of EEPs. This foreshadows an increased generation of e-waste in the near future (Orucho, 2023). Other government-led initiatives include programs such as DLP, Jitume, and CIH, which are all contributing to the intensified use of ICT devices such as laptops, desktops, and smartphones (Onyango & Munyungi, 2018). Despite the Bamako convention prohibiting imports of hazardous waste, additional e-waste is generated through illegal imports from other countries or through refurbished EEPs from countries like China and Europe (Anyango & Munyungi, 2018; Mwathi, 2014).

4.3 Collection of WEEE

The collection of e-waste is a challenging process, with recent statistics showing that only 12% of phone-based e-waste is collected in developed countries (Tanskanen, 2013). Studies further show that even in countries with established e-waste management systems collection of e-waste is still a big challenge (Forti, 2020). In Kenya, there are no good functional collecting schemes or public infrastructure for the collection of e-waste (Ofuya & Mulinge, 2023). For instance, in Nairobi, less than half of the e-waste generated daily ends up being collected, and mainly by the informal sector, does so in none non-structured way (Ofuya & Mulinge, 2023). Studies indicate that collection of e-waste from homes and municipal dumpsites is mostly done by informal collectors who are low-skilled personnel and who are often exploited (Ofuya & Mulinge) Efforts to implement a formal take-back model, initiated by Safaricom and Nokia to encourage the collection of e-waste from phones for safe handling and disposal, faced challenges primarily due to lack of legislative support (NEMA, 2010). The system entailed bringing back EoL phones to designated collection points in Nairobi and other specified parts of Kenya (Ogembo, 2010).

The lack of a formal collection mechanism has resulted in the accumulation of large stocks of e-waste at the consumer premises (Otieno & Omwenga, 2015; NEMA, 2010). While it is the responsibility of the government to develop guidelines that regulate the collection of e-waste, the enforcement of this regulation is weak, and NEMA has been termed a ‘toothless dog’ in this regard (Muniafu, 2016). Recently, the WEEE centre partnered with Carrefour stores in Nairobi County and the Eldoret National Polytechnic in Uasin Gishu County to expand its collection network and promote effective collection and pre-treatment of e-waste (WEEE centre, 2023). Previously, the WEEE centre had been involved in the collection of e-waste from government offices, corporate firms, and second-hand dealers for safe disposal (Ngila, 2020). To improve collection, Kaloki (2014) recommends in his study that a proper national and

institutional collection system is vital and should be put in place. NEMA is mandated by law to establish such a system that provides an effective collection of e-waste by implementing directives such as EPR (Kimeli, 2014). EPR strategy places the responsibility of e-waste collection, treatment, recycling, and disposal on the producer or manufacturer of EEPs (Gupt & Sahay, 2015).

Proper collection of e-waste can be done by individuals or registered groups who are trained and licensed to work within a regulated framework. The lack of regulation and structured collection systems means one can deliver to any interested buyer for any agreed pay, which encourages exploitation. One barrier that consumers face in delivering e-waste to collection centres is the distance from their homes to the collection point. This is as per the study carried out in Kenya by CDC Investment Works to establish how consumers manage e-waste (Bella, 2021). In light of this, consumers would prefer to be given incentives in the form of rewards or compensation for them to deliver e-waste to the centres. A five-year strategic plan developed by the government of Kenya is expected, besides other things, to guide in the building of capacity in a proper collection system for sustainable management of e-waste at the county and national level governments (KiPPRA, 2019).

4.4 Product Recovery

Product recovery is commonly understood as ‘re-use’ or refurbishment and is the second in the hierarchy of e-waste management strategy after ‘reduce’, which prioritizes the reduction of hazardous substances or pollutants, especially during the design stage of EEE (Modoi & Mihai, 2022). Key among the commitments that the government of Kenya has shown towards the promotion of product recovery is the adoption of the National Solid Waste Management Strategy, which aims, besides other objectives, to promote the re-use of products (Ofuya & Mulinge, 2023). The take-back system initiated by Safaricom, representing the private sector, was instrumental in pursuing this objective. The scheme supported the re-use of phones and related accessories (Cherutich, 2013). WEEE Kenya is a company that was initially licensed to collect e-waste, mainly computers, for refurbishment and re-distribution to Kenyan schools. The collected e-waste was added value and then resold for reuse (Kulecho & Khan, 2012).

Ofuya & Mulinge (2023) noted that due to the availability of cheap devices, consumers opt to buy new ones instead of repairing, stating that 70% of those who take EEPs for repairs were not willing to pay anything more than 20% of the cost of the new EEE. Considering this consumer behaviour, a study conducted by Omari et al. (2011) in Nairobi, Kenya, revealed that 37% of people ended up disposing of their WEEE due to the high cost associated with repairing the devices. Bella (2021) alluded to the stockpiling of e-waste in homes due to the lack of service and maintenance contracts and the low monetary value of the products, which makes repair uneconomical.

It has been observed that recovery and re-use of EEPs can significantly reduce the emission of major greenhouse gases (Park et. Al., 2019). Preventing e-waste generation, reducing its

volume, and promoting re-use can therefore alleviate the phenomena of environmental pollution and climate change. Additionally, manufacturing using recycled materials has been shown to require less energy compared to virgin materials, resulting in a corresponding reduction in the consumption of fossil fuels (Seif et al., 2023).

4.5 Material Recovery

Kenya's biggest challenge at the moment is that a large portion of e-waste is managed informally, where materials and components are harvested for use in the repair of EEE or for resale to scrap metal dealers (Muniafu & Miya, 2016). In this informal system, the downstream vendors selectively pick and dismantle specific EEPs to recover valuable parts from the discarded WEEE (Otieno & Omwenga, 2015). However, in this selective process, only e-waste with presumed value, as assessed by the scavengers, is salvaged while the rest is improperly disposed of. The consequence of such an approach is that low-value WEEE is thrown away, with some intrinsically valuable materials left unrecovered. One of the objectives of proper management of e-waste is the harvesting of precious and useful materials such as palladium and platinum for reuse. This process must be conducted in a safe environment with minimal negative effects on the environment (Modoi & Mihai, 2022). There is a proposal that the implementation of a circular economy model would address the aspects of resource optimization, which advocates for the re-use of materials, thus minimizing environmental pressure. The circular economy approach seeks to maintain the value of materials by circulating them within the system loop. (Koech & Munene;2020; Bella, 2021).

Tanskanen (2013) says a proper recycling process enables the recovery of valuable materials, which serves as a source of secondary material supply for use in manufacturing new products, which in a way injects efficiency into the value chain. This recovery of materials averts the use of primary raw materials, which is a saving of natural resources. In most cases, this cannot be affected because consumers are not aware of the savings in material in a proper recycling system that involves material recovery, hence a lack of support (Tanskanen, 2013). The presence of rare and valuable materials like gold, silver, palladium, and platinum and nonprecious ones like iron, copper, steel, and aluminum in WEEE has given birth to what is known as 'urban mining' where these materials are extracted from e-waste in landfills often found in urban areas (Franz & Silva, 2021; Massa & Archodoulaki, 2023).

4.6 Disposal

Kwame (2021) noted that one of the reasons things may get out of hand in the management of e-waste in Kenya is because of a lack of proper disposal systems. Many people would easily dispose of e-waste without considering the consequences of their irresponsible behaviour, which can lead to environmental and health hazards. Ofuya and Mulinge (2023) highlight that recycling activities are predominantly carried out by the informal sector, whose methods of disposal include re-selling, dumping in the dust bins or rivers, or burning them in the open air. Upon reaching their EOL, e-waste, especially from phones, has different proportions of substances, which complicates the disposal process. In Nairobi, a significant portion of e-waste

comprises phones, with a majority of them being used by repair technicians to scavenge for parts to fix faulty devices. Surprisingly, up to 75% of EoL electronics received by repair shops, which cannot be repaired or re-used in any way, end up being dumped indiscriminately with other solid wastes (Cherutich, 2013). When asked how they would dispose of their products once they were no longer in use, a study conducted in Kenya by Bella (2021) observed that 40% of the consumers would choose to burn them, while another 40% would simply bury or dump them carelessly. The disposal of e-waste by the Kenyan government MDAs usually follows established rules on procurement and disposal of items, where the items are bonded together with other items and disposed of through a competitive bidding process (Gathuka, 2013). Unfortunately, WEEE is disposed of as scrap metal in most cases.

In a study conducted by Anyango and Munyuki (2018), it was established that most disposal of e-waste was done using municipal solid waste (MSW) disposal systems and extended storage within institutional premises. Private companies and corporations may dispose of unused electronic and electrical items as donations to needy groups. There are no regulations currently in place governing e-waste donations. All formal recyclers in Kenya are based in Nairobi, which includes WEEE Kenya with a recycling capacity of 10,000 tonnes per year (Ofuya & Mulinge, 2023). WEEE centre handles e-waste from government institutions and private enterprises. Upon reaching their premises, WEEE is pre-treated where some parts, like the motherboards, are shipped abroad to companies that have the infrastructure to carry out proper recycling and disposal (Ongaji, 2023). The formal disposal process usually has the residue fractions either incinerated or buried in designated landfills in a fully controlled manner. It is important to note that any disposal option has its environmental effects that must also be managed well. For example, disposal by incineration causes air pollution (Tanskanen, 2013), and the lack of proper disposal mechanisms end up endangering both humans and livestock.

4.7 Legislation and Policy

The legal framework for e-waste management in Kenya is currently established through the 'Environment Management and Coordination Act' (EMCA) of 1999 (Revised 2015) and 'Waste Management Regulation' (2006) (Ofuya & Mulinge, 2023). The former Act provides for a coordinated approach in the implementation of existing environmental laws, for example, requirements for mandatory compliance with environmental regulations and provisions for handling waste, including disposal (Anyango & Munyungi, 2018). Under the Act, NEMA is given a legal mandate to issue and revoke certificates required for carrying out safe and sustainable management of waste (Macharia, 2014). Gathuka (2013) observes that while the Act is important in environmental conservation systems, it may fail because it relies heavily on coercion without consideration of other factors such as weak enforcement instruments and financial resources required to impose regulations. In 2010, NEMA developed 'Guidelines for E-waste Management in Kenya'. The guidelines were to form the basis for the development of regulations that would facilitate the enforcement of standards and procedures in the safe and

sustainable management of e-waste in Kenya. It provided guidance and set practical strategies for the proper handling and treatment of e-waste by all stakeholders (Onderi, 2011).

The Kenyan government has further demonstrated its commitment by enacting laws such as the 'Sustainable Waste Management Act of 2022'. Under the provisions of this act, manufacturers of EEPs are obligated to take responsibility for their products for the entire life cycle, including proper disposal of e-waste (Kenya Law, 2022). This Act also provides a framework for management initiatives and actions on waste, in both the national and county governments. This includes developing key guidelines and policies, allocation of roles and responsibilities for various actors, and handling producers regarding the EPR scheme, among other measures (Simidi, 2022). The draft 'Environmental Management and Coordination (E-waste management) Regulations, 2013' stipulates mandatory procedures for all-around safe management of e-waste up to disposal and coordination of various initiatives in the overall objective of its proper management (NEMA, 2013). The regulations have provisions for the control of EEPs in the country and the management of their EoL.

In the year 2019, MoEF did another draft of 'The National E-waste Management Strategy' that yet again sets out a 5-year plan for mitigating and managing e-waste. Kenya has also adopted the National Solid Waste Management Strategy, which is geared towards ensuring a healthy and safe environment for the citizens of Kenya through the sustainable management of solid waste (Ofuya & Mulinge, 2023). Cherutich (2013) has highlighted the need to develop effective e-waste policies and regulations that can be enforced both at the county and national levels Kenyan government. The situation in India was once similar to Kenya, where there was the existence of specific legislation on e-waste, but it lacked efficacy. However, over time, India progressively amended its regulations, specifically on EPR, to improve its performance (Borthakur & Govind, 2017). EPR lifts the burden of management of EoL products from government administration to producers or manufacturers, or their agents, called extended producer organizations (EPOs).

4.8 WEEE Management Challenges in Kenya

E-waste management in Kenya is currently facing numerous challenges and there is an urgent call to find an appropriate way of dealing with the challenges before they spiral out of control (Otieno & Omwenga, 2015) Lack of proper infrastructure, low awareness levels, inadequate technology or expertise for proper management of e-waste, inadequate funding and lack of stakeholder collaborations are just but a few of the challenges dogging the effort of proper management of e-waste in Kenya (Anyango & Waema, 2013). Ofuya and Mulinge (2023) identified dumping, inefficiencies within the public services concerned with environmental conservation, unregulated and uncoordinated actors, lack of proper support mechanism for collection of e-waste, lack of legislative framework for controlling influx of second-hand products, ineffective implementation of existing regulations and legislations, as well as shortage of technical expertise. Just like other developing Nations, Kenya has to grapple with

e-waste management challenges of the decade, partly due to the need to develop young industries and the increasing technological advancements of EEE (Hossain et al., 2015).

4.9 Rate of Increase in e-Waste Volumes

The primary concern in the management of e-waste, apart from its environmental impact, is the rate of increase in e-waste volumes (Borthakur & Sinha, 2013). With the rapid development of more powerful, convenient, and aesthetically attractive models of electronic devices and electrical appliances, EEPs quickly become technologically obsolete, leading to the rise in the purchase of new and refurbished products (Muniafu & Miya, 2016). New EEE destined for Kenya mainly originates from China, while refurbished units may come as donations from countries such as the UK (Muniafu & Miya, 2016). Modern consumers of EEE exhibit insatiable consumerism behaviour as compared to previous generations, making the turnover of EEPs continuously grow as the lifespan of EEPs becomes increasingly shorter (Bhutta et al., 2011). The increasing disposable incomes among the millennials add another dimension to the rising volumes of e-waste in Kenya (Asante, 2019).

Globally, the challenge of e-waste stems from the fact that it is the fastest-growing waste stream with a growth rate of 3-5% per year (Ambetsa, 2021; Ofuya & Mulinge, 2023). This is approximately three times the growth rate of solid municipal waste (SMW) (Ambetsa, 2021; Geoffrey et al., 2022) and accounts for about 1 % of SMW in developing countries (Muniafu & Miya, 2016). The current levels of e-waste in Kenya are not well documented, but generation per year was approximated to be about 51,000 tonnes in the year 2021 (Ofuya & Mulinge, 2023). The growth volumes are proportional to a set of valuable materials as well as hazardous materials they contain (Muniafu & Miya, 2016; Balde et al, 2015). The common trend observed in many developing nations is the disposal of e-waste without careful consideration of the value and potential hazards that the components possess (Muhani, 2012).

Access to low-quality and cheap electronic goods, along with the increasing population, has led to a drastic increase in the number of EEE imported from China and European countries in the last few years (Asimwe, 2012; Ofuya & Mulinge, 2023). Increased adoption of ICT by both private and public sectors for various applications because of the COVID-19 pandemic also contributed to the rising volumes of EEE (Adejumo & Oluduro, 2021). There has also been a rapid expansion and improvement of telecommunication services recently that has seen Kenyan consumers increase the use of mobile telecommunication equipment and the application of computer devices such as smartphones in households (Cherutich, 2013; Omwenga & Otieno, 2015). It is normally presumed that an increase in the acquisition and utilization of mobile communication devices has a corresponding proportionate increase in the volumes of e-waste generated. Mobile phone users, for example, rose from 24.9 million users in 2010 to 28 million in 2011 and may have increased more rapidly in the subsequent years. Coincidentally, this was the period that a national conference with a focus on e-waste management took place in Kenya (Kulecho & Khan, 2012). The increasing volumes of WEEE in developing countries such as Kenya are also thought to be due to large imports of second-

hand EEPs through legal and illegal channels. Studies indicate that about 50% of computers sold in Kenya are second-hand, further exacerbating the e-waste buildup crisis (Kulecho & Khan, 2012).

4.10 Unmanaged Entry Points of e-Waste Influx

The increasing numbers of EEE will result in the generation and accumulation of e-waste at EoL to an extent that will pose a management challenge. Besides the internally generated e-waste, Kenya suffers from the influx and proliferation of e-waste from outside the country. Studies indicate that up to 80% of e-waste in developed countries finds its way into developing countries for disposal. Kenya is one of the destinations (Lundgren, 2012). Much of the entry of e-waste into Kenya is facilitated by a lack of or weak WEEE-specific regulations allowing both legal and illegal e-waste trading and transboundary movements (Franz & Silva, 2022). It is acknowledged that Kenyan legislation on e-waste has not been adequate to cause good results in e-waste management efforts (NEMA, 2010). Some junk EEPs are still entering in the form of donations and end up being e-waste in a short time (Otieno & Omwenga, 2015; Franz & Silva, 2022). Lately, second-hand EEPs that cost a fraction of new products have gained entry through e-commerce platforms such as Jumia and Kilimall. Entry of WEEE into Kenya as a developing economy is further fueled by the high cost of treating e-waste in developed nations. The increasing numbers of obsolete EEPs will encourage and promote the informal treatment of WEEE putting the Kenyan population at risk due to the pollution of the environment. To successfully manage e-waste, the proliferation and transfer of used devices and appliances to developing countries must be checked with stringent legal infrastructure both at the local, regional, and international levels (Franz & Silva, 2022). If not checked, WEEE would put Kenya under an unproportionate burden in the coming years due to increasing rates of influx (Anyango & Munyugi, 2018).

4.11 Lack of Incentives for Re-use of e-Waste

Structured repair and re-use or re-manufacturing is considered a sound approach to the management of EoL electronics. In Kenya, the lack of formal supportive legislation for the repair and re-use of EoL electronics poses a challenge to the economy and the environment. Repairing of EEE maintains their value for a long time which is one way of optimally utilizing resources. WEEE is dismantled and re-used in Kenya by backstreet traders mostly found in urban centres who determine the value of e-waste and pay collectors based on their assessment. The collectors are often underpaid and work in poor conditions because of a lack of relevant legislation (Otieno & Omwenga, 2015; Omar, 2019). The European Union's Circular Economy Action Plan promotes the repair of EEE by addressing the need and the right to repair such as upgrading software and advocating for the reparation of EEE (Corsini et al., 2020). Some companies in Kenya attach a lot of value to the issue of proprietary software as a means of continuously earning revenues through periodical updates which is a challenge to be addressed in the whole process of managing e-waste. Muniafu and Miya (2016) suggested that incorporating a few incentives could foster the practices of proper e-waste management through reuse. Some incentives to promote sustainable reuse and repair of EEPs can be in the

form of improving occupational safety, upgrading skills of informal workers, and creating an environment that encourages re-use and repair of EEE through legislation, access to spares, and negotiating for good remuneration.

4.12 Lack of e-waste Treatment Infrastructure

Like in many developing countries WEEE in Kenya is treated informally using means such as open-air burning which has been classified as the most environmentally detrimental form (Wang et al., 2020). The easiest and most popular way that Jua Kali traders in Kenya extract copper from electrical cables is through open-air burning. The process releases hazardous airborne pollutants into the atmosphere (Balasubramanian & Karthik, 2016). The informal Jua Kali sector again cannot soundly manage e-waste because they lack the technological skills and capacity to treat the waste effectively and safely (Omar, 2019). As compared to the handling of metallic scrap, the complex composition of substances with different economic values integrated into e-waste materials makes it extremely hard to recycle and manage appropriately and would require complex infrastructure (Tanskanen, 2013; Shevchenko, et al., 2019). Kenya currently does not have the kind of formal recycling system that segregates and separates useful materials from non-valuable materials (Anyango & Munyugi, 2018). A lot of WEEE is handled by the informal sector and a few private treatment facilities which manage very small volumes as compared to the volumes generated (Anyango & Munyugi, 2018). For instance, the WEEE centre in Nairobi has managed to handle about 10,000 tonnes since its inception. The centre dismantles, separates, and exports WEEE in a controlled and safe environment. Kimeli (2014) identified poor infrastructure as being an obstacle to the sound management of e-waste in Kenya. Yet this far, Kenya has to fully recognize recycling as a viable industry, especially for EEEs. The national strategy on e-waste identified the need for county governments to build capacity in infrastructural systems for sustainable collection and management of e-waste (MoEF, 2019). Muniafu and Miya (2016) state that the reason why up to 68% of consumers stockpile e-waste in their households is primarily because of a lack of proper infrastructure in Kenya.

4.13 Informal Sector

Globally, 80% of the e-waste is managed by the informal sector (Otieno & Omwenga, 2015). This sector is a key player in Kenya's e-waste ecosystem. The informal e-waste recycling sector is often illiterate on environmental and safety issues. Their only concern is economic gains through the sale of valuable components (Wang, et al., 2020). The pre-treatment process as done by the sector is rudimentary and often lacks proper segregation skills and capacities, they disassemble the material using manual techniques and most e-waste ends up in municipal dumpsites (International Labour Organization (ILO), 2014). Recognition of the sector in sustainable e-waste management will address both the occupational and environmental challenges that the workers experience (Lundgren, 2012; Ofuya & Mulinge, 2023). Muniafu and Miya (2016) note that the sector has been neglected in Kenya and has not been given incentives to foster proper e-waste management. This sector hardly receives attention on e-waste management efforts but is often marginalized and harassed by police and municipal law

enforcement agencies (Ofuya & Mulinge, 2023). To facilitate proper management of e-waste in Kenya, there should be an enabling environment for the informal sector to operate and partner with formal social enterprises engaged in the safe handling of e-waste (Bastein et al., 2021). The informal sector has been shown by research to be strong and effective in collection, dismantling, and some functions within the preprocessing (ILO, 2014) It has to be involved and recognized to supply the e-waste value chain with secondary materials. Such an arrangement ensures that the informal sector receives the necessary training and support from the government leading to mutual benefits for all the parties involved.

4.14 Lack of Awareness of e-waste Risks and Disposal Systems

Numerous studies have reported a lack of or inadequate awareness of several aspects of sound e-waste management as being a major challenge (Anyango & Munyugi, 2018; Omar, 2019). A study conducted by Kiniti et al (2020) demonstrated how inadequate awareness has a substantial bearing on how people dispose of e-waste. Most people in Kenya treat WEEE just like regular solid waste and recklessly dispose them of in gardens, rivers, and by the waysides (Liza, 2015). Stockpiling of WEEE in houses and offices has also been traced to having its roots in a lack of awareness (Muniafu & Miya, 2016). Taskanen (2016) also says people are not aware that there is a saving in resources such as raw materials whenever e-waste is properly recycled. Increased awareness in Kenya is vital to ensure impacts of e-waste management are evident at the grassroots level.

4.15 Partial Compliance with International Conventions

The potential environmental and health risks that e-waste poses globally require focused attention and collaboration from all international players. International conventions, treaties, and agreements form the basis for governments to consider and develop legislative frameworks to address local existential and emerging e-waste challenges. The regulatory framework is key in the whole management process but the right approach has to be employed. The top-down regulatory approach which relies on a central authority for development and control of legislation has been proven ineffective when it comes to international management of e-waste which may respond better to a collaborative approach of all stakeholders including the private sector, manufacturers, etc., who can develop innovative ideas for safe and environmentally sound e-waste disposal approaches (Awasthi et al, 2019; Tetra Tech International Development, 2021). International regulations and conventions serve only as important reference point tools for promoting standardization in the way e-waste should be managed at the local level. They also help in defining specific roles of all parties involved at the global level (Franz & Silva, 2022).

Kenya is a signatory to a number of important international conventions such as the Basel Convention on the control of transboundary movements of hazardous wastes and their disposal (Ofuya & Mulinge, 2023), the Stockholm Convention on persistent organic pollutants, the Bamako Convention on the ban on of importation of hazardous substances to Africa (Ofuya & Mulinge, 2023). Partial adherence to international regulatory conventions is another challenge

to Kenya's pursuit of sound e-waste management especially on the control of cross-boundary movements (Muhani, 2012). Transboundary movement of WEEE due to illegal shipping and donations of equipment nearing EoL is worsening the e-waste problem in Kenya. The illegal entry of EEPs without proper documentation detailing the substances they contain inherently hampers the effective implementation of the provisions outlined in the Basel Convention. The lack of enforcement of environmental regulations in Kenya has been attributed to factors such as inadequate funding to the relevant government agencies (Ofuya & Mulinge, 2023).

4.16 Inadequate Financing or Funding Mechanism

The rate of obsolescence and complexity of materials making up e-waste is high and therefore, financial costs associated with their safe treatment outweigh the anticipated economic gains. A challenge Kenya is facing when executing policies regarding e-waste management is the lack of a financing mechanism (Omar 2019; Ofuya & Mulinge, 2023). Government agencies responsible for overseeing the policy implementation often face an acute lack of financial resources, hindering their ability to carry out essential activities like enforcing regulations. Enforcement of regulations requires huge funding and where such financial support is lacking, vices such as corruption thrive slowing or completely hindering the implementation process of functional e-waste management (Omar, 2019; Gathuba, 2013). To circumvent the challenge, sustainable funding mechanisms such as EPR are required where laws obligate the manufacturers or producers to take responsibility for what is known as the 'polluter-pays' principle of carrying the economic burden of sound e-waste management activities (Tanskanen, 2013). Kenya has proposed the implementation of the EPR system under Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) Regulation 2021 which is under development. It will stipulate the roles of various actors including EEE producers and how the take-back system will be implemented (Macharia, 2021).

4.17 Culture

Japanese EEE consumers are known to be highly sensitive to e-waste and have developed a strong recycling tradition, enabling the country to achieve a recycling rate of 75% (ACE-TAF, 2019; Doan et al., 2019). In contrast, Kenyan culture exhibits a unique tendency to avoid responsibility for the proper treatment of e-waste. This cultural inclination has led to the stockpiling of e-waste in people's houses and warehouses, with studies showing that about 50 % of e-waste is kept in homes. This habit presents a lot of danger as some of the WEEE may contain batteries or other hazardous substances that worsen with time, leading to issues like battery leaks (Omari, 2019). The habits are developed and sustained by the emotional value that the owners attach to the EEE. This emotional attachment, referred to as 'nostalgic value' by Tanskanen (2013) arises when EEP is no longer functional or serving its purpose but the owner chooses to retain it due to financial expenditure incurred in acquiring or the belief that e-waste may be useful in some other way in the future (Balasubramanian, et al, 2016; Omari, 2019). Studies show that most Kenyans would prefer staying with e-waste even after repair technicians have declared them useless (Kimeli, 2014). Another unique cultural aspect in Kenya that aggravates the problem of e-waste build-up in the country is the practice of

disposing of EEPs, especially mobile phones, not because they are no longer functional, but because something technologically better is available in the market and is affordable. This behaviour hastens the speed of e-waste obsolescence. Moreover, Kenyan consumers prioritize affordability over durability and reliability when choosing to buy EEPs (Asiimwe, 2010). These further compound the problem of e-waste as most such expensive products end up having a relatively short lifespan, and yet firms keep importing them to sustain their profits and operations (Muniafu & Miya, 2016).

4.18 Inadequate Policy and Legislative Interventions

The inadequate regulatory and policy interventions have largely been blamed as the cause for the poor management of e-waste in Kenya. The deficiency has been singled out as the main reason for the uncontrolled illegal inflows of second-hand EEE that have turned Kenya into a dumping ground for e-waste. (Omari, 2019). E-waste management is anchored in Article 42 of the Kenya constitution (2010), which guarantees the rights of every citizen to a clean and healthy environment that must be protected for the benefit of posterity (Opondo, 2020). Other policies and legislation that address some aspects of e-waste include the National Environmental Policy (2013), the Environmental Management and Coordination Act, 1999 (Revised 2015), Waste Management Regulations (2006), National E-waste guidelines (2011), National Solid Management Strategy (2015) (NEMA, 2014). Others are the National E-waste Strategy (2019) and the Draft E-waste Regulation. The National E-waste Guidelines of 2011 were aimed at enhancing public awareness as well as guiding practical aspects of sound e-waste management (Opondo, 2020). and the National ICT policy of 2006 requires vendors or operators to demonstrate readiness to undertake actions aimed at minimizing the environmental impact caused by their infrastructure (Macharia, 2021). The National ICT Policy of 2019 underscores the potential of emerging technological advancements but fails to acknowledge some challenges, such as a buildup of e-waste (MoICT, 2019).

Acts such as the Environmental Management and Coordination Act (1999) are often ineffective and have failed to facilitate the proper treatment of e-waste due to a lack of capacity or goodwill by the enforcing agencies (Gathuba, 2013). Waema & Mureithi (2008) note that existing policies and legislation do not adequately empower crucial government agencies, limiting their capacity to effectively manage e-waste. The existing regulatory framework does not adequately address issues such as EoL effects of government-owned EEE, which end up being weakly managed under the Public Procurement and Asset Disposal Act, 2015 (Muniafu & Miya, 2016; Kwame, 2021; Macharia, 2021). Scrutiny by experts has identified that, despite the existence of guidelines and policies, there is still a need for the establishment of laws and instruments that would impose adequate punitive measures to ensure the implementation of proper e-waste management requirements (Ngila, 2020; Opondo, 2020).

5. CONCLUSION

Kenya is already facing a crisis as a result of toxic effluents contaminating its water bodies and climate change impacts. In addition to these issues, emerging challenges related to e-waste

management are becoming increasingly apparent. Government programs and initiatives on ICT have inadvertently promoted the buildup of internally generated WEEE to unprecedented levels, weak regulatory frameworks and porous entry points have further exacerbated the problem by facilitating illegal dumping of WEEE in the country. These and other challenges require urgent attention and a multi-sectorial approach to effectively address them before they spiral to levels beyond control. While Kenya has made commendable efforts to promote environmental sustainability, a critical review of the current state of e-waste management practices in the country revealed existing gaps. We propose the following recommendations, informed by the review, towards the implementation of safe and environmentally sound management of e-waste in Kenya:

Establish Collection Centres: The government should consider supporting and possibly subsidizing the initial establishment and licensing of accessible and well-distributed localized collection centres where WEEE can be collected and segregated. This will ease logistical issues within the value chain, addressing the challenges associated with an overly centralized system. The implementation of the approaches is expected to foster an increased collection of e-waste. The government should view this as an initial critical step towards the successful implementation of a sound e-waste management system in Kenya. The government should also take steps to promote and legally compel consumers, repair technicians, and businesses to dispose of e-waste appropriately and in a responsible manner.

Public-Private Partnership: To establish a robust and sustainable e-waste infrastructure, the government should consider facilitating collaborations and involvement of key stakeholders at every stage of the WEEE life cycle, i.e., generation, collection, transportation, recycling, and disposal. The collaborative effort will mitigate the consequences of e-waste and manage the increasing volumes in the country. It is also important to regularly have a social dialogue with private firms, industries, educational institutions, academia, civil societies, experts, and local informal players in the development of economically viable infrastructure for e-waste management and in the crafting of supportive policy instruments.

Review Regulator Framework: Legislative stock-taking and review with a view to carrying out periodic amendments and reforms will be essential in removing barriers similar to what is currently hampering the proper and speedy implementation of directives. Through such audits, weak areas may be identified and improvements made. For example, it has been reported that NEMA is currently lacking adequate enforcement capacities in some aspects.

Support EPR Scheme: The EPR strategy can be implemented effectively using PROs, considering their local presence. PROs can be given targets depending on their market share and be required to give regular indicators of their performance. This approach will incentivize PROs to actively participate and be held accountable.

Enhance Awareness Programs: More awareness should be created among the various stakeholders on risks and the handling of e-waste. Knowledge of e-waste risks is significant in influencing positive behaviour and responsibility. Elaborate awareness campaigns among the young people in technical colleges through shows and electronic media will enable the upbringing of a generation that is properly schooled on matters of e-waste and also facilitate change in negative cultural behaviours, thus making the youth a strong advocacy team. E-waste day, the 13th of every October, should be marked with debates and discussions in various forums to raise awareness. With enough awareness, consumers can themselves be willing to voluntarily supply e-waste to scrap dealers or collection points, but the government has to influence through serious campaigns.

Involve Informal Sector: The role of the informal sector has to be recognized, and efforts should be made to integrate informal industry into mainstream e-waste management. The process should include training and empowerment, technically and financially. This will safeguard their health and those of others as well as the environment. Tapping into the numerical pool of Jua Kali artisans and the involvement of scrap metal dealers could easily be a resource of advocacy for a clean environment, increasing collection levels. As a government initiative, good and standardized sheds should be built for repair technicians who are licensed to promote repair and re-use strategies.

Support Jua Kali Sector: Jua Kali workers earn their livelihoods through WEEE, and is essential to be protected against overexploitation. To achieve this, the recycling activities of Jua Kali should be institutionalized and structured to operate within the framework of a government ministry with clear guidelines. This arrangement will elevate the Jua Kali sector to be a dignified institution where people earn decent incomes instead of being marginalized socially and economically. Their health and occupational issues need to be guaranteed by the government through formal schemes like the NHIF.

Adherence to Multilateral Agreements: There is a need to establish mechanisms that ensure compliance with and enforcement of international directives such as the Basel and Bamako Conventions, particularly on the importation of second-hand products. A local legislative framework should be enacted that takes into consideration the quality of legally imported second-hand EEPs and guidelines specifying requirements for EEPs that are allowed for donations locally and how to be treated at EoL.

Clarity in Trade Policies: Stringent policies should be put in place to regulate the importation and handling of secondhand EEPs. Local legislation should outline requirements for the inclusion of information such as date of manufacture, whether the item is refurbished or not, and disclosure of hazardous substances and provision for their acceptance.

Introduction of Training Programs on E-waste: Develop curriculum modules in technical colleges and universities to entrench e-waste management and develop requisite skills for

handling e-waste across the value chain. Institutions of higher learning are one of the largest generators of e-waste. Additionally, youth are vulnerable to the impacts of e-waste, often due to a lack of awareness which leads to irresponsible handling and disposal practices of e-waste.

Adopt the Circular Economy Model principles: Transition towards a circular economy or system, which is the best approach to e-waste management. A government task force should be appointed to spearhead and oversee the implementation of circular economy principles.

The suggestions are expected to enable the Kenyan government and environmental actors to develop adequate intervention measures for addressing the immediate and future challenges in e-waste management.

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